

Diamond Light Source Experimental Report

MM25913: Electric Octupole resonant forbidden diffraction as a possible new probe of 4f hybridization

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Date of Experiment

Thu 9 Apr 2020

Instruments

I16

1. Abstract

We have recently observed a feature in the Gd L1 XAS spectrum of gallium gadolinium garnet (GGG) that we believe, on the basis of energy and anisotropy, and theoretical modelling, to be the first example of electric octupole resonance in x-ray spectroscopy^[1]. Specifically, the peak is thought to arise from interference between dipole and octupole events, driven by hybridization between the highly localized 4f and delocalized 6p orbitals. This is indicative of bonding between 4f states and neighbouring oxygen ligands. While evidence for this interpretation appears sound, several aspects of the work are novel and observation of the same spectral feature by an alternative technique would be extremely valuable. We performed such a study using resonant forbidden x-ray diffraction. We attempted to observe resonant forbidden scattering^[2] at the Gd L1 edge, corresponding to E1E3 interference. By collecting a very large number of datasets and applying a special algorithm, we were able to obtain resonance spectra at the Gd L3 and L1 edges from the resonant forbidden 006 reflection, that were relatively free from parasitic multiple scattering intensity. No clear signal was observed at the expected energy of the E1E3 resonance, although it may have been obscured by residual multiple scattering and the tails of the (stronger) quadrupole resonant peak.

2. Experiment details

All measurements were performed on a large, polished GGG crystal with 001 surface normal, purchased from MaTecK GmbH. Incident beam polarization was horizontal with a vertical scattering plane (sigma polarization). A Dectris Pilatus3 detector was used throughout, with no polarization analysis, and the incident energy tuned to each of the three Gd L edges.

By far the most significant difficulty with the measurements was the ubiquitous multiple scattering, which varies rapidly with the sample azimuthal orientation, and is made worse by the relatively large unit cell parameter ($a = 12.3829 \text{ \AA}$). We developed a special data collection and analysis strategy to remove multiple scattering signals and reveal the pure the resonance spectra. Central to this approach are the assumptions that multiple scattering varies very rapidly with the sample azimuthal angle, and that it always increases the overall signal strength. The key steps were:

- For each photon energy, the resonant forbidden 006 reflection was measured *via* a very rapid, continuous, 'theta' scan.
- The measurements were repeated over a set of azimuthal angles in a region predicted to be relatively free from multiple scattering.
- Data from any scan leading to an atypical peak width were rejected.
- The underlying resonant signal was taken to be the *minimum* peak area for the range of azimuthal angles, unless this corresponded to one of the extrema, in which case the data were rejected.

3. Results

This approach yielded a very good L3, and quite reasonable L1, spectrum.

The L1 spectrum is central to the current study. While the results showed some sharply-varying intensity (Fig. 2) in the low energy part of the spectrum, the important energy range of $\sim 8.36 - 8.40$ keV was found to be remarkably clean.

Figure 1: The 006 resonant forbidden diffraction spectrum at the Gd L3 edge, and corresponding fluorescence signal.

Figure 2: The 006 resonant forbidden diffraction spectrum at the Gd L1 edge, and corresponding fluorescence signal.

The L1 resonance spectrum (Fig. 2) showed a clear dipole feature above the edge, at ~ 8.398 keV. The lower energy peak, at ~ 13 eV below the peak in the fluorescence signal is identified as a quadrupole resonance, by comparison with Refs. ^[1,3]. The E1E3 peak ^[1] would have appeared at an energy of 8.371 keV in the measured spectrum. There is no clear evidence for this peak from the data. However, it is likely that a very weak peak from this resonance would have been obscured by the tail of the quadrupole peak.

4. Conclusions and future work

While the current method was very successful in revealing weak resonant scattering on a very strong multiple scattering background, it was unable to reveal the elusive E1E3 resonant peak. In fact, the technique is based on the slightly dubious assumption that multiple scattering intensity is always additive, hence neglecting the possibility of destructive interference between the two processes.

Multiple scattering remains a serious hindrance to the measurement of weak diffraction features, and the approach presented represents only a partial solution to this problem.

Full details of the measurements and analysis can be found in the accompanying Jupyter notebook^[4].

5. References

- [1] A. Juhin et al ‘Measurement of f orbital hybridization in rare earths through electric dipole-octupole interference in X-ray Absorption Spectroscopy’
A. Juhin, S.P. Collins, Y. Joly, M. Diaz-Lopez, K. Kvashnina, P. Glatzel, Ch. Brouder, and F. de Groot
Phys. Rev. Materials **3**, 120801(R) (2019)
- [2] V.E. Dmitrienko, K. Ishida, A. Kirfelc and E.N. Ovchinnikova, *Acta. Cryst.* **A61**, 481–493 (2005).
- [3] R.F. Pettifer, S.P. Collins and D. Laundy, *Nature* 454, 196-199 (2008)
- [4] S. P. Collins 10.5281/zenodo.6008935

6. Publications resulting from this work

See ^[4].